
A Comprehensive Report on Elliptic Curve Cryptography (With Rust Implementation)

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Keywords: Public-Key Cryptography · Elliptic Curve Cryptography · ECC Security · Digital Signature · Public and Private Keys

Abstract

Among a number of cryptographic techniques, the technique of ECC has emerged as one of the leading cryptographic schemes due to its strong performance and security attributes. This paper presents an overall survey regarding elliptic curve cryptography wherein in-depth evaluation is covered on theoretical grounds, practical implementations, and security aspects thereof. The ECC theoretical framework has been explained, considering algebraic properties of elliptic curves, mathematical functions involved in ECC algorithms. Further, the cryptographic systems based on ECC have been elaborated, that is key exchange, digital signature, and encryption, in order to bring out the central ideas of those and the impediments encountered during operation. Further, some practical aspects related to the ECC approach will be considered, including key generation, key management, and computational complexity. This paper also discusses Rust implementation of different algorithms for ECC and their benefits for IOT devices

1 Introduction

Fast community technology has enabled the transmission of multimedia content including snap shots, audio and video over a couple of networks however most of these transmissions take area over insecure networks, posing risks together with lack of statistics, interruptions (e.g., unauthorized copying and distribution), and likely mutations [1, 2]. Especially Of wonderful concern within the areas of big facts and cloud infrastructure [three, four Although traditional encryption techniques which include Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) and Data Encryption Standard (DES) are used for day-to-day security, how they're used in multimedia contexts method that complex pixel correlation and large facts volumes. Recognizing these obstacles restrained via a -characteristics, researchers have explored opportunity approaches, that specialize in systems based totally on an it's miles too violent. These structures offer specific characteristics which includes sensitivity to preliminary situations, ergodicity, combined attributes, easy analytical descriptions, and especially robust behaviors, making them promising candidates for multimedia safety has developed [3, 4].

Since its advent in 1978, the RSA set of rules introduced via Rivest, Shamir and Adleman [5] has served as the primary approach for digitally encrypting and signing. However modern-day RSA set of rules an implementation has revealed a few shortcomings, together with the need to use huge key lengths to enhance the safety of the cryptosystem. On the contrary, Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) solves those shortcomings with a key smaller implementations at the same time as retaining similar safety over ECC algorithms and public key cryptography consequently generated via elliptic curves are effectively blended via mathematical computation (as determined in RSA) with computation which has been replaced by way of in corporations Breaking virtual signatures poses a extra bold project , due to the expanded difficulty to resolve the discrete logarithm hassle in elliptic curved organizations in comparison to factoring big numbers of high factors.

1.1 Report Directions

This paper provides a comprehensive examination of Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) across several key domains:

1. **Encryption Schemes:** We analyze ECC-based encryption protocols, focusing on their implementation with reduced key sizes while maintaining robust security guarantees in modern cryptographic protocols.
2. **Digital Signatures:** We examine the generation and verification of digital signatures using ECC, particularly exploring the computational hardness of the discrete logarithm problem in elliptic curve groups and its role in providing secure authentication and non-repudiation mechanisms.
3. **Asymmetric Hyperchaotic Image Encryption:** We investigate specialized image encryption schemes leveraging ECC, analyzing their advantages over traditional cryptographic approaches for multimedia security.
4. **IoT Applications:** We explore the implementation of ECC crypto-processors in real-time IoT environments, focusing on hardware optimization and practical deployment considerations for resource-constrained devices.
5. **Future Prospects:** We conclude by examining emerging trends in elliptic curve cryptography, with particular attention to its potential role in post-quantum cryptographic systems.

2 Cipher Scheme

The Elliptic Curve Integrated Encryption Scheme (ECIES) protocol represents a standardized adaptation of the ElGamal encryption system [6]. Consider a scenario where Subject A wishes to transmit a secure message mes to Subject B. The protocol requires several prerequisite components and information, which we detail in the following subsections.

- **MAC:** A message authentication code sent alongside the data to verify its integrity.
- **KFC:** A key derivation function that enables the creation of multiple keys from a single reference secret.
- **SYM:** A shared-key algorithm.
- **E ($\mathbb{F}_p$):** An elliptic curve utilized as a shared-key algorithm with key generator G , where $\text{ord}_p(G) = n$.
- **PK_B :** Public key of B, defined as $PK_B = PK_B \cdot G$, where $PK_B \in [1, n - 1]$ would be B's secret key.

2.1 Data Encryption Procedure

To start with the message encryption mes , Subject A proceeds as follows:

1. Take a random number r which belongs to the range $[1, n - 1]$ and compute $C = rG$.
2. Calculate $Z = r \cdot PK_B$.
3. Generate the keys gk_1 and gk_2 so that $(gk_1, gk_2) = \text{KDF}(\text{abscisse}(Z), C)$.
4. Encode the message m by executing $J = \text{SYM}(gk_1, m)$.
5. Compute the MAC code $t = \text{MAC}(gk_2, J)$.
6. Finally, send (C, J, t) to Subject B.

2.2 Data Decryption Procedure

To decrypt the received message (C, J, t) , Subject B must perform the following calculations:

1. Start by verifying if $C \in E(F_p)$; otherwise, reject the message.
2. Compute $Z = PK_B \cdot C = PK_B \cdot rG = rPK_B$.
3. Generate the keys gk_1 and gk_2 such that $(gk_1, gk_2) = \text{KDF}(\text{abscisse}(Z), C)$.
4. Compute the MAC code $t' = \text{MAC}(gk_2, J)$.
5. Check that $t = t'$; otherwise, deny the message.
6. Finally, decipher the message by calculating $M = \text{SYM}^{-1}(gk_1, J)$.

3 Digital Signature

Various algorithms exist for implementing digital signatures with elliptic curves. These algorithms will be used for the performance analysis. Yanbo Shou [7] demonstrated in his thesis that the Weierstrass equation representing an elliptic curve can be streamlined for working in a finite field with many points, where F_p becomes:

$$E : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b, \quad (1)$$

where a and $b \in F_p$. Since the elliptical curve group is a cyclic group, remember to add two points and multiply the points by a scalar.

3.1 Key Generation in the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA)

We consider the elliptic curve referenced in (1). The key generation process using elliptic curves is carried out as follows:

1. Choose a random number r that is strictly less than the order n of the curve.
2. Calculate P along with $P = rG$, where G acts as the curve's generator.

Therefore, our key pair is (P, r) , where P represents the public key and r denotes the private key. Note that P along with the parameters n, a, b , and G must be published.

3.2 Creating a Signature Using the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA)

To create the signature S of a message mes , proceed as follows:

1. Select an arbitrary value r in the range $[1, n - 1]$.
2. Compute $R(a_1, b_1)$ where $R = rG$.
3. Calculate $c = a_1 \pmod n$. If $c = 0$, return to step 1.
4. Calculate $r^{-1} \pmod n$.
5. Compute $\text{SHA-1}(\text{mes})$ and convert it to an integer e (alternatively, SHA-256 or SHA-512 can be used instead of SHA-1).
6. Calculate $s = r^{-1}(e + ac) \pmod n$, where a is the secret key. If $s = 0$, return to step 1.

The signature S of the message mes is the pair (c, s) .

3.3 Verification of an Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) Signature

To verify the signature $S = (c, s)$ for the message mes using the public parameters, perform the following steps:

1. Check if c and s are integers within the range $[1, n - 1]$.
2. Calculate $SHA-1(mes)$ and convert it to an integer e .
3. Compute $w = s^{-1} \pmod n$.
4. Calculate $u_1 = ew \pmod n$ and $u_2 = rw \pmod n$.
5. Compute $X(a_1, b_1)$ where $X = u_1G + u_2P$.
6. Check if $X = 0$ to confirm the validity of S ; if $X \neq 0$, calculate $v = a_1 \pmod n$.

The signature S of the message mes is legitimate if $v = c$ [8].

Key Length (bits)	Computational Time (sec)
163	0.19
233	0.23
283	0.17
409	0.20
571	0.13

Table 1: Running time for key generation in rust.

4 Asymmetric Hyperchaotic Image Encryption Scheme

This section describes a method for securely transmitting an image. The sender scrambles the image (encryption) and generates a unique fingerprint (hash) of the original image. They then use the receiver’s public key to encrypt the fingerprint and combine it with the scrambled image into a single package, which is subsequently sent over an open channel, such as the internet [9].

On the receiving end, the recipient uses their private key to decrypt the fingerprint and then applies both the fingerprint and a specific decryption process to reconstruct the original image. Figure 1 illustrates this entire process.

Figure 1: Example for the Transmission Process [9]

This approach explains the image scrambling (encryption) through two main techniques: permutation and diffusion [10].

Permutation Permutation shuffles the image data. It changes not only the location of each pixel but also mixes the bits within each pixel, adding another layer of scrambling (a diffusion effect). To enhance efficiency and security, the bits from each pixel are divided into different-sized groups before being shuffled.

Diffusion Diffusion utilizes chaotic sequences (pseudo-random data) to further scramble the image. The same sequences used in the shuffling process are reused here for efficiency. Starting from the bottom right corner and moving up and to the left, each pixel influences its neighbors in these directions, providing an added layer of complexity.

A figure (Figure 2) illustrates these detailed steps, with a highlighted section (green frame) demonstrating the novel technique of using differently sized blocks during permutation.

Figure 2: Algorithm Flow Chart [9]

5 Real-Time IoT Applications Using an Elliptic Curve Cryptography Processor

Security is especially important for real-time applications. These applications demand both high performance and low delays, while also needing to protect against cyberattacks on the numerous vulnerable points of IoT devices. Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) is a popular choice for securing IoT systems, as it provides methods for exchanging keys and digitally signing data.

For IoT applications, hardware acceleration for ECC becomes crucial. This means using specialized hardware to handle ECC algorithms more efficiently. The research described here introduces a new hardware architecture that supports various widely used ECC-based cryptography schemes. This design offers several improvements, including faster processing and protections against certain attacks. The researchers also verified their design on a development board and simulated its performance on different chip fabrication technologies.

5.1 Elliptic Curve Cryptography in IoT Application

An elliptic curve over the prime field $GF(p)$ is characterized by the Weierstrass equation [11]:

$$E : y^2 = x^3 + ax + b \pmod{p} \tag{2}$$

The variables a and b are whole numbers within the prime field $GF(p)$ and must satisfy $4a^3 + 27b^2 \neq 0 \pmod{p}$. A Weierstrass elliptic curve E over $GF(p)$ includes a collection of points $P = (a, b)$, where $a, b \in GF(p)$, along with an additional point O , referred to as the 'point at infinity.' The NIST P elliptic curves conform to the Weierstrass form over $GF(p)$, and their parameters are available in [12]. The collection of elliptic curve points, together with the point at infinity defines a group, governed by the following group law:

5.1.1 Point Addition (PA)

Let $P_1 = (a_1, b_1)$ and $P_2 = (a_2, b_2)$. Then the sum $P_1 + P_2 = P_3 = (a_3, b_3)$ is calculated as:

$$a_3 = \left(\frac{b_2 - b_1}{a_2 - a_1} \right)^2 - a_2 - a_1 \quad (3)$$

$$b_3 = \left(\frac{b_2 - b_1}{a_2 - a_1} \right) (a_1 - a_3) - b_1 \quad (4)$$

5.1.2 Point Doubling (PD)

For $2P_1 = (a_1, b_1)$, the result $P_3 = (a_3, b_3)$ is calculated as:

$$a_3 = \left(\frac{3a_1^2 + c}{2b_1} \right)^2 - 2a_1 \quad (5)$$

$$b_3 = \left(\frac{3a_1^2 + c}{2b_1} \right) (a_1 - a_3) - b_1 \quad (6)$$

Considering two points on the elliptic curve, $P_1 = (a_1, b_1)$ and $P_2 = (a_2, b_2)$, all arithmetic within this system (addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division) is performed over a prime field denoted by $GF(p)$. Point addition (PA) and point doubling (PD) operations on this group form the foundation for many elliptic curve cryptosystems.

As illustrated in Figure 3, a typical hierarchical structure for such a system exists. High-level protocols like ECIES and ECMQV reside at the top. The next layer includes point multiplication (PM) and double-point multiplication (DPM), which will be explained in further detail in Section 5.2. The core layer involves basic operations on elliptic curve points, specifically point addition (PA) and point doubling (PD). These operations are based on the lower layer of finite field arithmetic over $GF(p)$, including modular addition, subtraction, and multiplication. Importantly, our layered design places modular inversion together with PA and PD, as our implementation utilizes Fermat's Little Theorem, which depends on the processes from the foundational layer.

Figure 3: Typical hierarchical structure of an ECC-based IoT security system

5.2 Point Multiplication (PM) and Simple Power Analysis (SPA)

Point multiplication (PM) between an integral value r and an elliptic curve point P is the fundamental operation in all cryptographic schemes dependent on ECC. PM is denoted as $Q = rP$, representing the repeated addition of the point P to itself $r - 1$ times:

$$Q = rP = \{P + P + \dots + P\} \quad (\text{repeated } r - 1 \text{ times}) \quad (7)$$

Several algorithms are available for performing point multiplication, with the most well-known based on the Double-and-Add method. Rust Code 1 presents the Right-to-Left version of the Double-and-Add method for point multiplication.

Rust Code 1: Double and add from Right to Left

```

1 fn double_and_add(mut k: u64, p: (i64, i64), n: u64) -> (i64,
  ↪ i64) {
2     let mut q = (0, 0); // Q = O (point at infinity)
3     let mut r = p;     // R = P
4
5     for i in 0..n {
6         if k & 1 == 1 { // if k_i == 1
7             q = point_add(q, r); // Q = Q + R
8         }
9         r = point_double(r); // R = 2R
10        k >>= 1; // Move to the next bit
11    }
12
13    q
14 }
15
16 // Function to add two points on an elliptic curve (you'll need
  ↪ to define this)
17 fn point_add(p1: (i64, i64), p2: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
18     // Implement point addition logic
19     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
20 }
21
22 // Function to double a point on an elliptic curve (you'll need
  ↪ to define this)
23 fn point_double(p: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
24     // Implement point doubling logic
25     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
26 }
27

```

This work addresses vulnerabilities in Point Multiplication (PM) algorithms regarding timing and Simple Power Analysis (SPA) attacks. Rust Code 1 suffers from these issues due to its variable Point Addition (PA) count based on the key's Hamming weight and the distinction between PA and Point Doubling (PD) operations. SPA attacks [14] exploit power traces during PM execution to potentially reveal the secret key k by observing these operational differences. Timing attacks, unlike SPA, can be executed remotely by measuring response times. Our design prioritizes protection against both attack types.

The Double-and-Add-Always method [15] offers theoretical protection against timing attacks by performing dummy PA operations alongside real ones, as shown in Rust Code 2. However, it can still result in key information leakage due to point addition (PA) operations involving the point-at-infinity. In Rust Code 2, lines 2, 3, 7, and 8 highlight this vulnerability, where PA operations with the point-at-infinity could expose portions of k .

Rust Code 2: Double and add but Always from Right to Left

```

1 fn double_and_add_always(mut k: u64, p: (i64, i64), n: u64) ->
  ↪ (i64, i64) {
2     let mut q = (0, 0); // Q = O (point at infinity)
3     let mut t = (0, 0); // T = O (point at infinity)
4     let mut r = p;     // R = P
5
6     for _ in 0..n {
7         if k & 1 == 1 { // if k_i == 1

```

```

8         q = point_add(q, r); // Q = Q + R
9     } else {
10        t = point_add(t, r); // T = T + R
11    }
12    r = point_double(r); // R = 2R
13    k >>= 1; // Move to the next bit
14 }
15
16 q
17 }
18
19 // Function to add two points on an elliptic curve (you'll need
20 ↪ to define this)
21 fn point_add(p1: (i64, i64), p2: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
22     // Implement point addition logic
23     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
24 }
25
26 // Function to double a point on an elliptic curve (you'll need
27 ↪ to define this)
28 fn point_double(p: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
29     // Implement point doubling logic
30     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
31 }

```

To further mitigate the vulnerabilities, we propose a modified Double-and-Add Rust Code 3 [13]. This version includes a flag (`one_flag`) that tracks whether a '1' has been encountered in the key. When `one_flag` is 0, dummy PA operations are performed. When it becomes 1, real PA operations occur, but only when a '1' is present in the key. This approach eliminates PA operations with the point-at-infinity, enhancing protection.

Rust Code 3: Modified Double and add but Always from Right to Left

```

1 fn modified_double_and_add_always(mut k: u64, p: (i64, i64),
2 ↪ n: u64) -> (i64, i64) {
3     let mut q = (0, 0); // Q = 0 (point at infinity)
4     let mut r = point_double(p); // R = 2P
5     let mut one_flag = false; // one_flag = 0
6
7     // Step 1: Handle the least significant bit (k_0)
8     if k & 1 == 1 {
9         q = p; // Q = P
10        one_flag = true;
11    }
12
13    // Step 2: Loop through remaining bits
14    for _ in 1..n {
15        k >>= 1; // Move to the next bit
16
17        if k & 1 == 1 {
18            if one_flag {
19                q = point_add(q, r); // Q = Q + R
20            } else {
21                q = r; // P + R, Q = R

```

```

21         r = point_add(p, r);
22         one_flag = true;
23     }
24     } else {
25         if one_flag {
26             q = point_add(q, r); // Q + R
27         } else {
28             r = point_add(p, r); // P + R
29         }
30     }
31     r = point_double(r); // R = 2R
32 }
33
34 q
35 }
36
37 // Function to add two points on an elliptic curve (you'll need
38 ↪ to define this)
39 fn point_add(p1: (i64, i64), p2: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
40     // Implement point addition logic
41     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
42 }
43
44 // Function to double a point on an elliptic curve (you'll need
45 ↪ to define this)
46 fn point_double(p: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
47     // Implement point doubling logic
48     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
49 }

```

Our implementation also supports Double Point Multiplication (DPM), which is necessary for ECDSA verification, combining two PMs and one PA operation. The double-point multiplication equation is given by:

$$Q = kP + lR \quad (8)$$

Here, Q , P , and R are three distinct elliptic curve points, and k and l are two scalars. Our implementation employs a constant-time variant of Shamir's trick, outlined in Rust Code 4.

Rust Code 4: Using Shamir's Trick

```

1  fn shamir_trick(
2      k: u64, l: u64,
3      p: (i64, i64), r: (i64, i64),
4      s: (i64, i64)
5  ) -> (i64, i64) {
6      let mut q = (0, 0); // Q = 0 (point at infinity)
7      let mut t = (0, 0); // T = 0 (point at infinity)
8      let mut s_plus_q = point_add(s, q); // S + Q
9      let n = k.leading_zeros().min(l.leading_zeros()) as u64;
10     ↪ // Find the most significant bit (bit length)
11
12     // Step 1: Loop through the bits
13     for i in (0..n).rev() {
14         q = point_double(q); // Q = 2Q

```

```

15     // Handle the conditions based on the bits of k and l
16     let k_i = (k >> i) & 1;
17     let l_i = (l >> i) & 1;
18
19     if k_i == 1 && l_i == 1 {
20         q = point_add(q, s_plus_q); // Q = Q + S
21     } else if k_i == 1 && l_i == 0 {
22         q = point_add(q, p); // Q = Q + P
23     } else if k_i == 0 && l_i == 1 {
24         q = point_add(q, r); // Q = Q + R
25     } else {
26         t = point_add(t, s); // T = T + S
27     }
28 }
29
30 q
31 }
32
33 // Function to add two points on an elliptic curve (you'll need
34 ↪ to define this)
35 fn point_add(p1: (i64, i64), p2: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
36     // Implement point addition logic
37     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value
38 }
39
40 // Function to double a point on an elliptic curve (you'll need
41 ↪ to define this)
42 fn point_double(p: (i64, i64)) -> (i64, i64) {
43     // Implement point doubling logic
44     (0, 0) // Placeholder return value

```

6 Conclusion

Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) emerges as a compelling alternative to RSA for asymmetric cryptography due to its efficiency and robustness. ECC provides the same level of security with much shorter key lengths, making it highly suitable for resource-limited environments such as embedded systems. This paper introduced two applications of ECC: an innovative image encryption method and a high-performance ECC crypto processor. The encryption scheme utilizes ECC to safeguard critical parameters while ensuring robust protection against various attacks. The crypto-processor design offers efficient hardware acceleration for core ECC operations, including countermeasures against side-channel attacks. Both implementations demonstrate the advantages of ECC for secure and efficient cryptographic solutions.

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